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3D Graph Theory Analysis unveils the role of structure-dependent contact resistances in conductive polymer composites[†]

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Metallic filler particles form continuous paths in non-conductive elastomers and provide electrical conduction. The resulting conductive polymer composites (CPCs) are useful as flexible and stretchable conductors or strain sensors. A critical filler loading φ_c must be reached for such composites to become electrically conductive. Percolation theory accurately describes the changes in conductivity close to φ_c but fails to predict conductivities above this transition. Here we show that Graph Theory (GT) metrics can be used to correlate network structure and macroscopic electrical conductivity above φ_c . We used FIB-SEM tomography to reconstruct statistically representative networks in $(31.5\ \mu\text{m})^3$ large CPC volumes that contain 2.5- μm -diameter silver spheres at loadings between 27 vol% and 52 vol%. We find linear correlations between the number of nodes and edges and the average graph degree, length, efficiency and current-flow betweenness with the conductivity of CPCs. We correlate these metrics with and formulate a simple model that describes the increase in conductivity above φ_c in terms of network morphology. Kirchhoff circuit analysis on the extracted graphs reveals that the change in network topology alone cannot explain the experimentally observed changes in macroscopic conductivity. We show that the average particle-particle contact resistance scales reciprocally with graph degree. This suggests that the filler loading affects contact areas or tunneling widths, providing a link between mechanical and electrical network properties.

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1 Introduction

Conductive polymer composites (CPCs) contain conductive filler particles in a non-conductive polymer matrix. They combine electronic conductivity with the elastic deformability of the matrix material and are used in piezoresistive sensors¹, electronic packaging², chemical sensors³, batteries⁴, and as electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding⁵. The electrical and thermal conductivities σ of CPCs depend on the size and shape of the filler particles and their distribution in the matrix⁶.

It is often helpful to predict and manipulate the electrical conductivity σ as a function of filler loading, shape, and arrangement. Certain applications require flexible conductors with high conductivities at minimal filler loadings to reduce costs, achievable e.g. with segregated filler networks⁷. Piezoresistive sensors⁸, on the other hand, require CPCs with electrical resistances that predictably change upon mechanical deformation. Our goal is to predict the conductivity of CPCs from the structure of the conductive filler network.

CPCs require the formation of a continuous (percolating) network of particles to enable electronic conduction. Such filler particle networks (FPNs) form when the volume fraction of filler dispersed in the matrix exceeds a critical filler loading φ_c . Above this percolation threshold, the bulk CPC conductivity σ increases by several orders of magnitude, and the CPC turns from an insulator to a conductor. This transition has been studied in detail, discussed in excellent reviews, and is not the focus of this contribution^{6,9–11}.

Far above this insulator-to-conductor transition, σ is dominated by particle-particle contact resistances R_C ^{12,13}. They depend on local contact mechanics, which is a function of nanoscale geometry, the interactions between fillers, and external forces. Short-ranged filler-filler interactions, often dominated by van der Waals forces¹⁴, affect them; researchers have approximated these interactions, e.g., using Lennard-Jones (LJ) potentials to obtain realistic particle spacings¹⁵.

Fig. 1 3D reconstructions of an FPN with 1370 silver particles of $2.5\mu\text{m}$ diameter in a PDMS matrix. (A) 350 BSE images were merged into a 3D stack with 350^3 voxels. Thresholding converted this stack into (B) binary 3D volume that was (C) labelled using watershed segmentation on the distance-transformed binary volume to identify individual particles. The (D) adjacency matrix A_{ij} was extracted using MATLAB, and the first ten entries are shown here. The adjacency matrix completely describes an (E) graph $G(n,e)$ that is represented as a 3D plot with true particle positions here, and (F) nodes are connected via edges.

It is not yet possible experimentally to measure individual contact resistances R_C in FPNs. Previous models often assumed that R_C does not depend on ϕ and attributed changes of $R_C(\phi)$ to network geometry^{16,17}. Recently, we used destructive tomography and advanced image segmentation on CPCs containing silver micro-spheres to show that the average contact resistance $\overline{R_C}$ between filler particles are a strong function of silver loading ϕ_{Ag} when increasing loading above percolation¹³. The 3D filler network was approximated with a set of parallel conductive paths, and their tortuosity was analyzed using 3D-reconstructed volumes. The number and average length of electron transport paths, alongside the loading-dependent CPC conductivities, were then used to approximate the average particle-particle contact resistance¹³.

Approximations such as the parallel path model are useful, but they risk neglecting important features of the conductive network (for example, crossings and dead ends). More in general, it remains a challenge to interpret the increasingly detailed and large datasets that describe 3D FPNs and link their geometry to the conductivity of CPCs. A promising strategy for analyzing such FPNs is Graph theory (GT), which has recently been used to relate material properties to the geometry of complex random networks^{18,19}. Graphs are combinations of nodes and their connecting edges, and make up the complex networks formed in, e.g., composite materials. It is conceivable that certain macroscopic properties of composite materials that are set by the filler particle network²⁰ can be predicted by analyzing network properties using GT. Recently, optical and electron microscopy of materials' microstructures have been employed to extract graphs and corresponding GT metrics from nanoparticle gels¹⁹. The authors varied preparation conditions such as salt concentration and found strong cor-

relations of connectivity GT metrics in nanoparticle gels with the material's resistivity¹⁹.

To our knowledge, graph theoretical metrics have not been applied to FPNs in CPCs. It appears likely that the three-dimensional structure of FPNs has properties that can be described with such metrics and are relevant for their electromechanical properties. Our goal in this contribution is to identify correlations between GT metrics and material properties that are relevant to the understanding and application of CPCs.

This paper is structured as follows: We first review our previously introduced method to extract filler particle networks (FPNs) from actual CPCs using the well-established combination of focused ion beam (FIB) cutting and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for FIB-SEM tomography¹³. Here, we introduce a new post-processing algorithm for the resulting 3D dataset, which is then analyzed to extract mathematical graphs. This reduces the data volume from gigabytes to kilobytes. Our algorithm distinguishes connected from disconnected particles to build the full, complex contact network, rather than the parallel-path approximation discussed previously¹³. In the first part of the network analysis, we employ graph-theoretical metrics to describe the properties of the filler network. The change of all metrics with filler loading is then compared with the experimentally measured electrical bulk conductivities. We present strong correlations that are discussed with a simple model that relates topological changes with filler loading to higher conductivities. In the second part of the network analysis, we show Kirchhoff simulations on the reconstructed conductive filler networks. Equivalent resistor networks are solved to reconstruct the average particle-particle contact resistance $\overline{R_C}$ as a function of filler loading ϕ_{Ag} . The results are compared to earlier, simplified models that as-

sumed purely parallel paths to draw conclusions about the role of the particle-particle contact resistance versus network structure that dominates the electrical conductivity of CPCs.

2 Results and discussion

Tomography and graph building

Recently, we fabricated CPCs with spherical silver microparticles of an average diameter of $2.5\mu\text{m}$ in a silicone elastomer matrix using previously established methods¹³. Electrical four-point measurements were conducted to obtain conductivities at varying filler loadings φ_{Ag} . Percolation at a critical filler loading of $\varphi_{\text{C}} = 36\text{vol}\%$ resulted in $\sigma = 7.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{S} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$; the maximal conductivity of $\sigma = 6890 \text{S} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$ was reached at the highest filler loading of $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 52\text{vol}\%$. Note that the maximal filler loading is limited by the reachable packing density of the silver particles; voids formed when it became too high.

We employed FIB-SEM tomography to reconstruct subvolumes of the FPNs. A gallium ion beam intermittently removed material slice by slice, and we recorded backscattered electron (BSE) images of the cross-sections²¹. The images were subsequently aligned, tilt-compensated, cropped, and filtered to obtain volumetric images (cf. SI). Each volume was $31.5\mu\text{m} \times 31.5\mu\text{m} \times 31.5\mu\text{m}$ large and its physical voxel size was 90nm . Figures 1(A)-(C) illustrate how a typical (3D) BSE image (Figure 1(A)) was segmented to a (3D) binary image (Figure 1(B)) and converted to a (3D) “label image” (Fig. 1(C)). The particles in the binary image are connected, and each voxel represents a binary value indicating whether the volume is filled with silver or not. The label image contains individual particles that have been separated and labelled with unique numbers.

The binary and label images (figs. 1(B)+(C)) were analyzed by a custom algorithm to determine which particles were connected (see experimental section). It searches for adjacent voxels in the label image that have different labels but are in direct contact in the binary image. For example, particles “4” and “5” in Figure 1(C) were connected in the binary image (see insert of Figure 1(B)). The corresponding entry of the adjacency matrix $A_{4,5} = 1$ indicates that they are connected neighbors. Our algorithm scanned the entire label image for connected pairs and computed an adjacency matrix $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{G})$. The adjacency matrix is a symmetrical, $N \times N$ matrix²² whose entries A_{ij} follow²³

$$A_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if nodes } i \text{ and } j \text{ are connected through an edge} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The size, N of $A(\mathbf{G})$, corresponds to the number of detected particles. Figure 1(D) shows the first ten entries A_{ij} of \mathbf{A} for the label image from figure 1(C).

Three different FPNs were analyzed for each silver loading in the range of $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 27 - 52\text{vol}\%$. For each FPN, an adjacency matrix was extracted and used to build graphs $G = \{n, e\}$ ²², where $nG = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N\}$ is a set of N nodes and $eG = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_M\}$ a set of M unordered pairs of elements of eG , i.e., the edges connecting different nodes in nG . In this work, nodes correspond to particles and edges to particle-particle contacts. Figure 1(E) shows a 3D plot of $G(n, e)$ constructed from the adjacency matrix

$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{G})$ extracted from Figure 1(C). Nodes (black) are plotted at the centers of gravity of the particles’ location in 3D space, and edges (blue) connect different nodes as in figure 1(F).

Graph theoretical metrics

We described the conductive FPN as an undirected graph $G(n, e)$ ²² and analyzed its metrics. First, we applied “connection” and “distance” metrics²⁴ that describe different properties of the graph. We plotted the metrics as a function of silver loading φ_{Ag} to assess their topological changes (Figure 2).

The number of nodes N (Figure 2(A)) corresponds to the number of particles in the FPNs, including those that are not connected to any other particle. It increased from $N = 1054 \pm 73$ for $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 27\text{vol}\%$ to $N = 1839 \pm 277$ for $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 52\text{vol}\%$. This is consistent with the expected proportional increase of particle numbers in any given sub-volume of a CPC with φ_{Ag} for uniform particles in the large-number limit. The result is useful for verifying the overall graph reconstruction procedure.

The number of edges M (Figure 2(B)) enumerates particle-particle contacts within the FPN. It increased from 1675 ± 135 for $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 27\text{vol}\%$ to 4141 ± 333 for $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 52\text{vol}\%$. The saturation of M for $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 48\text{vol}\%$ and $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 52\text{vol}\%$ indicates geometrical limits for the homogeneous dispersion of particles. Scanning electron micrographs (see Figure S5 in the S.I.†) indicate the presence of air-filled pores at filler loadings above $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 48\text{vol}\%$ as previously reported¹³. This is a common issue in conductive inks and decreases the mechanical stability of a print²⁵.

The average graph degree \bar{k} describes the connectivity of $G(n, e)$ in more detail. It is the average over all local degrees k_i of single nodes and indicates the average number of edges per node²²:

$$\bar{k} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N k_i. \quad (2)$$

This metric is equivalent to the average coordination number Z , defined as the average number of particles in contact with a center particle, that can be calculated from radial distribution functions²⁶.

Figure 2(C) shows that \bar{k} increased from 3.18 ± 0.12 to 5.00 ± 0.03 in the range of $\varphi_{\text{Ag}} = 27 - 48\text{vol}\%$. A small decrease between $36\text{vol}\%$ and $38\text{vol}\%$ is likely due to the metric becoming sensitive to fluctuations close to φ_{C} . The decrease of \bar{k} above $48\text{vol}\%$ to $\bar{k} = 4.53 \pm 0.31$ indicates the packing limit at around $48\text{vol}\%$. We analyzed isolated particles in the FPN with $k_i = 0$ and found that most were due to boundary effects, where contacts of particles at the edge of the 3D reconstruction were not detected.

Similar trends have been reported for CPCs in literature: the increase of $\bar{k}(\varphi)$ in silver-bakelite CPCs was analyzed using 2D optical micrographs by Gurland²⁷. They found that the coordination number Z increased from $1.3 - 1.5$ to above 2.5 for $\varphi_{\text{C}} = 36 - 38\text{vol}\%$. It is not possible to directly infer 3D coordination numbers from these measurements, and comparison of 2D to 3D values is perilous²⁸, but the qualitative trend of greater \bar{k} (or Z) with φ verifies however that a more interconnected FPN yields higher electrical conductivities.

The spatial distribution of filler particles with finite volumes

Fig. 2 Connection and distance metrics of CPC FPNs as a function of filler loading ϕ_{Ag} : (A) number of nodes N , (B) number of edges M , (C) average graph degree \bar{k} , (D) Average graph length \bar{L} , (E) graph efficiency E , (F) assortativity coefficient r and (G) current-flow betweenness \bar{b} . Illustrations in dashed boxes show the definitions of the respective metric.

is never truly random. Literature on random percolation usually assumes point-like particles (

site percolation) that occupy a lattice with a random probability²⁹. Such models do not consider attractive forces that are common between physical filler particles and e.g. cause agglomeration³⁰. The metallic microparticles that we use here are at least weakly attractive because of the short-range van der Waals forces³¹. It challenging to quantify the deviations from randomness that such interactions cause using optical³² or electron microscopy³³ in 2D. Microscopists tend to verify homogeneity and non-randomness by eye and look for apparent agglomerates.

We tested whether GT metrics can be used to objectively quantify the 3D randomness and agglomeration state of particles in CPCs, minimizing human bias. The average coordination number \bar{Z} is a suitable measure to describe the agglomerate strength, i.e., the average coordination number plus the packing density³⁴. Yang et al.³⁴ studied individual agglomerates that were not connected within an FPN and found that both metrics decay exponen-

tially with agglomerate size and higher packing densities led to higher coordination numbers, ultimately increasing the agglomerate strength. Our FPN contain agglomerates that may be interconnected and bridged by single particles, rendering the average coordination number inadequate for non-randomness characterization.

Other metrics have been specifically developed to quantify the non-randomness of general graphs. Zhang et. al.³⁵ computed individual node-degree correlations and quantified the network using the “degree-specific assortativity coefficient” r_G ³⁶,

$$r_G = \frac{\sum_{ij} ij(e_{ij} - a_i b_j)}{\sigma_a \sigma_b}, \quad (3)$$

which ranges from -1 for a fully disassortative to 1 for a fully assortative network with $\sigma_a = \sigma_b$ the standard deviations in a_i and b_i ³⁶. It indicates whether nodes of the same degree k preferentially connect (assortative mixing) or, on the contrary, nodes of

dissimilar degree are more likely to be connected (disassortative mixing)³⁶ (Figure 2f). The assortativity coefficient is commonly expressed through the degree-mixing matrix \mathbf{e} , where e_{ij} is the fraction of edges that connect nodes of degree i to degree j . For undirected networks, \mathbf{e} is a $k_{max} \times k_{max}$ symmetric matrix, where k_{max} is the largest degree in the graph $G(n, e)$. It satisfies the sum rules

$$\sum_{xy} e_{ij} = 1, \sum_j e_{ij} = a_i, \sum_i e_{ij} = b_i, \quad (4)$$

$a_i = b_i$ for undirected networks equals the fraction of “edge-ends” that connect via nodes of degree i . Every edge has two ends; using them rather than single edges avoids double-counting of edges (node with $k = 2$ to node with $k = 3$ is symmetric).

A standard definition of “true” randomness in the field of networks uses Erdős–Rényi graphs³⁷. The degrees of such graphs have Poisson distributions, i.e., nodes of a given degree are connected with independent probability in the graph²², and their assortativity coefficients are $r_G = 0$ ³⁸. Attractive forces between particles can cause the clustering of nodes, which invariably increases r_G above zero. Because the inner structure of FPNs is complex, the contributions of agglomerate size, shape, concentration, and relative location on r_G need to be considered separately. A quantitative analysis would require systematic creation and analysis of synthetic microstructures, which is out of scope for this manuscript. We state qualitatively that increasing the connectivity of agglomerates reduces r_G until the network becomes entirely random. Although the presence of agglomerates already is a non-randomness, the way multiple agglomerates connect to larger structures reduces randomness. This may be due to the limited size of our FPNs, so more systematic studies are needed to give proof.

Figure 2(D) shows the assortativity coefficient (in yellow) for our FPNs as a function of filler loading φ_{Ag} . All graphs show weak assortative mixing, i.e., $r_G > 0$, with values close to zero for all φ_{Ag} . This indicates that our FPNs are almost entirely random, which we verified by visually inspecting the 3D reconstructions. The positive values of r_G likely indicate weak agglomeration of particles, which are governed by physical interactions between the particles. Abadi and Ruzzenenti³⁹ simulated such attractive particle systems that exhibit agglomeration (max. r_G was 0.25) and deagglomeration (min r_G was 0.07) as a function of temperature. The authors showed that the agglomeration is well-described by the assortativity coefficient. More theoretical and experimental work on actual particle networks is, however, needed to define the limits for agglomerated particle systems.

In summary, the connection metrics indicate that increasing the silver loading in our FPNs increased the particle density, the number of particle-particle contacts, and the average number of contacts per particle. The FPN remained essentially random, with deviations probably caused by weak agglomeration. In the following, we compare these connection metrics to distance metrics to cover additional aspects relevant to transport properties.

“Distance-based” metrics analyze “paths”. Any connection between two nodes through edges is a path²². Shortest paths are defined as the minimum distance $d_{i,j}$ between two nodes $i \neq j$, i.e., the smallest number of edges between nodes i and j . For

undirected graphs, $d_{i,j} = d_{j,i}$; isolated nodes have $d_{i,j} = \infty$. A distribution of node-to-node distances $d_{i,j}$ is shown in figure S3 in the SI; in the following, we consider the average graph length

$$\bar{L} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{ij} d_{i,j}. \quad (5)$$

The evolution of $\bar{L}(\varphi_{Ag})$ in Figure 2(E) appeared almost as an inversion of $\bar{k}(\varphi_{Ag})$. In the range of $\varphi_{Ag} = 27 - 36 \text{ vol\%}$, \bar{L} decreased continuously from 13 ± 0.57 to 10 ± 0.37 , following a slight increase to 10.34 ± 0.01 at 38 vol\% . It continued to decrease until a minimum of $\bar{L} = 8.45 \pm 0.47$ was reached at $\varphi_{Ag} = 52 \text{ vol\%}$, and remained almost constant between 48 vol\% and 52 vol\% . Increasing silver loading reduced the average number of edges that need to be traversed in transport. This implies that many particle-particle contacts in the FPN do not contribute to transport, and that the fraction of these “non-conducting” contacts increased with silver loading.

The efficiency E of a graph, introduced by Latora and Marchiori⁴⁰, focuses on the reciprocal sum of shortest paths between all node-pairs in $G(n, e)$,

$$E = \frac{1}{N \cdot (N - 1)} \sum_{i \neq j} d_{i,j}^{-1}, \quad (6)$$

normalized between 0 and 1. Isolated particles with $k = 0$ do not contribute to E , as $d_{i,j}^{-1} = 0$, while all other $d_{i,j} \neq \infty$ add to the efficiency. There is an interesting analogy to the overall resistance of a parallel resistor network, which is also a reciprocal sum. Increasing the number of parallel conductive paths leads to an increase in E .

We found $E(\varphi_{Ag})$ (Figure 2(F)) to continuously increase from 0.037 ± 0.0015 for $\varphi_{Ag} = 27 \text{ vol\%}$ to 0.061 ± 0.0012 for $\varphi_{Ag} = 48 \text{ vol\%}$. Beyond 48 vol\% , $E(\varphi_{Ag})$ decreased significantly to $E = 0.049 \pm 0.0045$ for $\varphi_{Ag} = 52 \text{ vol\%}$, probably due to pores that interrupted paths and extended paths, which decreased E .

The average graph length or efficiency is based on shortest paths; however, real networks do not necessarily operate in this manner⁴¹. Centrality metrics classify nodes, for example by counting how many paths pass through a certain node, and consider all (not only the shortest) paths. The “current-flow betweenness” (centrality) considers such paths between node-pairs and mimics electrical networks: consider current flowing between a randomly chosen source node s and target node t . The current-flow betweenness b_i of any arbitrary node i is the average current $I_i^{(st)}$ that flows through i for all $s - t$ node-pairs⁴¹

$$b_i = \frac{\sum_{s < t} I_i^{(st)}}{\frac{1}{2} N(N - 1)} \quad (7)$$

with N being the number of nodes in G . This definition follows Kirchhoff’s laws for electrical networks⁴¹. It is also called “random-walk betweenness centrality” because it quantifies the frequency of a node in a random walk through the network⁴². All paths are considered by the metric, but shorter paths are weighted more⁴¹. The average graph length \bar{L} or efficiency E considers only shortest paths, which is electrically unrealistic, and both \bar{L} and ef-

efficiency E are strongly affected by inhomogeneities such as pores forming at high silver loadings (see figure 2(F)).

We computed the average current-flow betweenness \bar{b} over all node-pairs in our graphs, as shown in figure 2(G). It increased slightly from $2.24 \cdot 10^{-2} \pm 5.00 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to $2.27 \cdot 10^{-2} \pm 1.49 \cdot 10^{-3}$ within $\varphi_{Ag} = 22 - 27 \text{ vol\%}$ and then fell continuously until 52 vol\% , where it reached $\bar{b} = 1.18 \cdot 10^{-2} \pm 6.85 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Adding more particles to the FPNs increased the overall current flow in the networks. The current is more effectively distributed, rendering other paths less important for current flow, i.e., more paths of different lengths are present to transport electrical current efficiently.

In summary, adding more particles to the FPNs reduced the average path length, increased the efficiency of the graphs by adding more paths, and decreased the importance of individual nodes, so that a larger number of paths contributed to current flow and conductivity was less depending on a small number of conductive paths.

Correlation of GT metrics with conductivity

We are now in a position to correlate graph metrics with a macroscopic transport property, the electrical conductivity σ of CPCs. First, we test which of the metrics introduced above correlate with the conductivity in a black-box approach. We then use the physical interpretations of the GT metrics introduced above to draw conclusions on structure-property relations that explain the effect of FPN structure on conductivity. Note that we do not discuss the assortativity coefficient and measures of randomness, because they are not expected to predict conductivities. Their (weak) correlations are discussed in the S.I.†.

We only considered CPCs above the critical volume fraction $\varphi_C = 36 \text{ vol\%}$ for percolation, where the CPCs showed conductivities above $0.0076 S \cdot m^{-1}$. Macroscopic conductivities in the range of $0.0076 S \cdot m^{-1} - 6890 S \cdot m^{-1}$ ($\varphi_{Ag} = 36 - 52 \text{ vol\%}$) were measured on macroscopic samples using the four-point probe method. Linear correlations with different GT metrics were quantified using the Pearson correlation coefficient R^2 . Above $\varphi_{Ag} = 48 \text{ vol\%}$, air-filled pores formed in the CPCs prevented a homogeneous dispersion of particles in the PDMS matrix, which affects R^2 . We neglected metric values for the highest silver loading (yellow circles) and only correlated metric values within a conductivity range of $\sigma = 0.0076 - 5315.80 S \cdot m^{-1}$ (green circles).

Figure 3(A) shows that the total number of nodes N correlated positively, but weakly ($R^2 = 0.63$) with σ . This metric describes the non-normalized volume fraction. It indicates that particles that were added randomly do not necessarily contribute to percolating networks that increase conductivity.

The number of edges M correlated positively and strongly ($R^2 = 0.93$) with σ (figure 3(B)). This implies that a fraction of edges contributes to conductivity and continuously reinforces FPNs. This fraction does not drop strongly, leading to a strong $\sigma - M$ correlation.

The average degree \bar{k} (the average number of edges per node) provides a global, summarized overview of the network's connective state. It correlated positively and strongly ($R^2 = 0.92$) with

σ (Figure 3(C)), similar to the $\sigma - M$ correlation. More interconnected FPNs exhibited greater \bar{k} that were more conductive, even though \bar{k} does not directly quantify transport properties. In the case of homogeneous particle dispersion and in the absence of porosity, the metric proved to be a good predictor for CPC conductivity.

“Connection” metrics probe aspects of networks that are not necessarily relevant for electrical transport. “Distance” metrics are closer to conduction mechanisms, with different metrics being closer to different conduction mechanisms. Strong correlations with a certain metric suggest a different transport scenario. We can thus use the R^2 of the correlations to assess which topological aspect of the FPN dominates CPC conductivity.

The average graph length \bar{L} correlated negatively and strongly ($R^2 = 0.88$) with σ (Figure 3(D)). Shorter average electron transport paths, i.e., a shift of $d_{i,j}$ to the left, increased the conductivity. Fewer particle-particle contacts are needed to traverse the network. The exact number of “saved” particle-particle contacts is not known and cannot be directly recovered: \bar{L} decreased e.g. from 9.62 to 8.46 by 12%, while σ increased from $2262 S \cdot m^{-1}$ to $5315 S \cdot m^{-1}$ by 235% (within $\varphi_{Ag} = 42 - 48 \text{ vol\%}$). The relative changes of \bar{L} (12%) and σ (235%) differ by one order of magnitude; if the networks were dominated by the average of the distance distribution, their relative changes should be similar. \bar{L} remained constant above $\varphi_{Ag} = 48 \text{ vol\%}$, but conductivity rose to $6890 S \cdot m^{-1}$, suggesting that the average path-length is not the dominant factor driving conductivity changes. This is not surprising: dead ends, i.e., individual particles that form the end of a path ($k = 1$), contribute to \bar{L} but not to conductivity.

The graph efficiency E considers the number and length of shortest paths, dead ends and cross-connections. Eq. 6 implies that adding paths of shorter length L result in higher E . Dead ends can be directly measured by counting the number of nodes with only a single edge, i.e., $k = 1$. We found that the amount of dead ends decreases with increasing CPC conductivity (see S.I.† for more details, Figure S6). The number of cross-connections cannot be assessed directly, because it refers to nodes of $k > 1$. Increasing the number of cross-connections between identical paths increases E as more edges are added, while not necessarily changing \bar{L} . E was a good predictor for the conductivity due to its strong ($R^2 = 0.85$) positive correlation with σ , as shown in 3(E). Note that both \bar{L} and E correlated similarly strongly with σ ($R^2 = 0.88$ and $R^2 = 0.85$). Dense and reinforced networks with an increased density of cross-connections have shorter conductive paths, which increases E and σ . We hypothesize that the changes in cross-connection are therefore relatively small, and the topological changes in the FPNs are dominated by the addition of new, shorter paths.

The largest absolute correlation with σ ($R^2 = 0.93$) was found for the current-flow betweenness \bar{b} . It quantifies the trend of individual nodes becoming less critical for current flow with increasing silver loading, lowering \bar{b} . It appears to be advantageous when the current is more uniformly distributed throughout the network. This extends the observation found in literature¹¹ that close to percolation, many particles in CPCs hardly contribute to conductivity; changes in network structure that involve larger

Fig. 3 Correlations of the (A) number of nodes N , (B) number of edges M , (C) average graph degree \bar{k} , (D) assortativity coefficient r_G , (E) average graph length \bar{L} , and (F) efficiency E with bulk CPC conductivity σ .

fractions of particles in conductivity are thus highly beneficial. Far above percolation, enable many paths appears to be important still. Robustness is a third implication: if an arbitrary particle is removed from a network with a small \bar{b} , the overall current can still take other paths without suffering large losses.

The strong correlation of \bar{b} and σ indicates that few short paths do not dominate the conductivity above percolation as they are characterized by \bar{L} and E , but instead paths of different lengths in general. This is proven by the stronger correlation of $\sigma - \bar{b}$ compared to $\sigma - E$. We recommend the current-flow betweenness as a predictor and hypothesize that this metric will be useful in other CPCs that use different filler materials and geometries as well.

Finally, we revisit the recurring deviation of all GT metrics at $\varphi_{Ag} = 52 \text{ vol}\%$: the fact that \bar{k} and E both deviate despite their different structural targets suggests a qualitative change in the CPC microstructure. Pores apparently reduce the number of particles while maintaining the number of contacts, thereby reducing \bar{k} for $\varphi_{Ag} = 52 \text{ vol}\%$. Interestingly, the average graph length \bar{L} and current-flow betweenness were less affected. Likely, the particle density is locally increased around pores, which adds longer paths but has a negligible effect on \bar{L} . This is probably because also more particles in the matrix, which yield smaller paths. Symmetrically adding paths on both ends of the path-length distribution (see figure S3 in the SI), i.e., smaller paths due to more particles and longer ones due to porosity, will not change \bar{L} or \bar{b} , indicating a saturated state.

Kirchhoff simulations and contact resistances

We found linear correlations of metrics with macroscopic CPC conductivity. To test whether this linearity also holds on the microscopic scale, we performed Kirchhoff simulations on the mathematical graphs $G(n, e)$, using the reconstructed graphs in the form shown in Figure 1(E) as input. Nodes lying on opposed faces of the probed volume were wired to connector nodes with applied potential differences (Figure 6(A)). Kirchhoff's laws were iteratively solved using a custom algorithm (see experimental methods for details).

We first assumed a constant $R_C = 1 \Omega$ for all particle-particle contacts and calculated overall resistances of the FPNs reconstructed at different φ_{Ag} . These were related to electrical conductivity using $R = \rho \frac{\text{length}}{\text{area}}$ (with $\sigma = \rho^{-1}$) with the sample's cube geometry (length = $31.5 \mu\text{m}$, area = $(31.5 \mu\text{m})^2$). This microscopic "material" property, $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$ captures the networks geometry in far more detail than the macroscopically measured CPC conductivity σ .

Figure 5 shows correlations of network metrics from each graph with its corresponding network conductivity $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$ obtained from the Kirchhoff simulations. Circles represent the graphs that were only microscopically connected and not macroscopically, i.e., these graphs correspond to FPNs extracted from CPCs below the critical filler loading $\varphi_{crit.}$. Squares represent graphs that were macroscopically connected, i.e., electrically conductive CPCs above $\varphi_{crit.}$. Their color corresponds to the experimentally measured CPC conductivity $\sigma_{\text{experimental}}$.

The numbers of nodes (figure 5(A)) and edges (figure 5(B)), the degree (figure 5(C)) and the efficiency (figure 5(E)) corre-

Fig. 4 (A) Wiring of the graphs in the Kirchhoff circuit: Opposed nodes (red and blue) are connected via zero-weight edges and a potential difference is applied to calculate the network resistance R_{Net} . (B) Zoom in on an individual particle path in the FPN overlaid with the equivalent path in the graph showcasing the different electrical contributions in the Kirchhoff simulation, i.e., the particle resistance R_P and the contact resistance R_C .

Fig. 5 Correlations of the (A) number of nodes N , (B) number of edges M , (C) average graph degree \bar{k} , (D) average graph length \bar{L} , (E) efficiency E and (F) current flow betweenness b_i with predicted conductivity $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$ from the Kirchhoff simulations. The circles represent microscopically connected (non-conductive), the squares macroscopically connected (conductive) networks with their color representing their experimentally obtained CPC conductivity.

lated with $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$. Correlation was moderate for the nodes and efficiency ($R^2 = 0.74$ and $R^2 = 0.72$, respectively) and strong for the edges and degree ($R^2 = 0.92$ and $R^2 = 0.94$, respectively). Graph length (figure 5(D)) and current-flow betweenness (figure 5(F)) had very strong negative correlations and very strong ($R^2 = 0.96$ and $R^2 = 0.92$, respectively) with $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$. Note that the trends are comparable to those in Figure 3), where we correlated the metrics with a measured material property instead of a predicted one, but the functional form of the connections changed from linearity in the measured material property to power-law behavior in the predicted material property. Note also that the metrics describing the graph's geometry are considered implicitly

in the Kirchhoff simulation. The only component of the simulation that could explain its deviation from the experiment is the particle-particle contact resistance R_C .

The results of predicted electrical conductivity $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}(\varphi_{Ag})$ at a constant $R_C = 1 \Omega$ for the range of $\varphi_{Ag} = 38 - 52 \text{ vol}\%$ are shown in Figure 6(A) (squares) and compared to the experimentally measured conductivities (circles). Predicted σ increased from 121407 Sm^{-1} to 276360 Sm^{-1} by 227%. In the same loading range, experimental CPC conductivity increased from 696 Sm^{-1} to 6890 Sm^{-1} by 990%. There exists no single R_C for all φ_{Ag} to match the predicted conductivities to experimental ones. R_C must therefore depend on silver loading, and decrease with increasing φ_{Ag} .

Fig. 6 (A) Experimental $\sigma_{\text{experimental}}$ (circles) and predicted $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$ (squares) electrical conductivity from Kirchhoff simulation using $\bar{R}_C = 1\Omega$. The σ value for $\varphi_{Ag} = 36.1 vol\%$ is not shown because it differs by five orders of magnitude. (B) Average (particle-particle) contact resistance \bar{R}_C as a function of silver loading φ_{Ag} from Kirchhoff simulations (circles) and from the parallel path model (triangles) computed in tortuosity analysis in our previous work¹³.

We repeated the Kirchhoff simulations and varied R_C to match the experimental conductivity (figure 6(B)). The $\bar{R}_C(\varphi_{Ag})$ from the Kirchhoff circuit analysis on the complex network (circles) gradually decreased from 174.36Ω to 40.11Ω , in the silver loading range of $38.8 - 52.3 vol\%$.

The average contact resistance \bar{R}_C calculated using the complex network and Kirchhoff simulation was five times above values calculated from the parallel path model (figure 6(B)). In the parallel path model, connections are approximated using the average number and length of paths that form parallel chains, assuming uniform particle diameters. This could have many explanations: the actual particle diameter varies by $\pm 0.72 \mu m$ (see the S.I. in our previous work¹³), indicating that the number of possible contacts is greater, which lowers $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$ in the parallel path model⁴³. Another explanation could be that cross-connections are prohibited in the assumed cubical structure in the parallel path model. Cross-connections increase the average path-length, which again, lowers $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$. Approximating the magnitude of both effects is rather difficult. All shortcomings of the parallel path model are indirectly addressed in the complex network: a parallel path approximation without cross-connections is not required, as the particle size is irrelevant; only the contact location with other particles is utilized in the complex network.

We have previously demonstrated that increasing the silver loading increased the average contact spot diameter between particle-particle contacts that subsequently led to less current-restrictions in our FPNs¹³. We hypothesized that the reinforcing nature of adding more particles led to this phenomenon, but at that time, we were unable to quantify this effect. The GT analysis shown here, coupled with the Kirchhoff circuit calculations, yields the same result, albeit from fundamentally different viewpoints. The parallel path model assumes a structure of tortuous, parallel paths that do not intersect and its metrics are the length and number of electron transport paths. Assuming a single particle

diameter leads to the number of contacts that yield $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$. The methods described here extract FPNs directly to find each particle location plus its physical size to build the network, additionally taking into consideration the cross-connections between neighboring paths. The network metrics that well-describe the FPN are then used to calculate $\sigma_{\text{predicted}}$ using Kirchhoff simulations.

3 Summary and Outlook

We conducted GT analyses on graphs corresponding to 3D-reconstructed FPNs in CPCs at different φ_{Ag} of spherical silver filler particles in elastomeric matrices. Previous work approximated the network by a set of parallel paths. Here, we used the full reconstructed physical networks to capture the FPN's full complexity. We physically interpreted the trends for selected GT metrics with filler loading through topological changes of the FPNs. Our GT metrics indicate that the FPNs closely follow a random dispersion of particles with little to no agglomeration present. Higher silver loadings resulted in a more robust network structure, where shorter and more parallel paths facilitated greater current flow and higher efficiencies.

We correlated and discussed transport metrics like graph length, efficiency and current-flow betweenness with bulk CPC conductivity σ and found the latter to be its best predictor. Correlations between different GT metrics yielded a microstructural model we used to understand the purely topological conduction mechanism in the CPCs.

Kirchhoff circuit analysis of the graphs revealed that smaller contact resistances are required at higher silver loadings to match the measured σ , which considers all topological descriptors from our GT analysis. This proves that the contact resistance between silver particles is the dominant factor in CPC conductivity, which aligns with our earlier observations that the contact area reduces current restrictions between silver particles.

We demonstrated that graph theory can be applied to study

the electrical conductivity in CPCs, marking the first use of 3D-GT in these network-driven materials to not only investigate the randomness of FPNs but also correlate metrics with macroscopic transport properties, such as electrical conductivity. As an outlook, we plan on investigating the role of filler segregation in CPCs. So-called segregated CPCs (s-CPCs) are undoubtedly the best strategy to yield the highest conductivity at minimal filler loadings⁷, and we expect that the particle-particle contact resistance, as shown here for conventional CPCs, is the driving force for conductivity in CPCs.

4 Experimental

Image processing The following section describes the workflow of the commercial software Avizo from ThermoFisher Scientific used previously¹³. Many terms are specific to this software.

3D reconstruction and post-processing of the raw data was carried out by cropping, slice alignment, shearing of the image stack, cropping to isotropic volume size of $350 \times 350 \times 350$ voxel, edge-preserving (non-local means) filtering, as shown in Figure 1a).

Since the CPCs contain only two phases, the 8-bit greyscale histogram contains two peaks separated by a minimum. The silver phase in the filtered BSE images was segmented using (greyscale histogram) thresholding and the threshold was set from the minimum between the two phases until a gray-value of 255, i.e., white. Since the minimum depended on contrast-brightness settings, it changed from sample to sample. The result of this procedure was a binary (3D) image as depicted in Figure 1b), where the silver phase voxels have a value of 1 and all others 0.

The next step was particle identification and performed directly on the binary image. This is typically achieved by combining the calculation of a distance map from the binary image with watershed segmentation. An in-depth description can be found in⁴⁴. We used the Avizo software and its "Separate Objects" module using the "Chamfer - Conservative" distance map and a marker extent of 1. The resulting image contained separate particles. The particles were then individually labeled with unique numbers. Groups of voxel connected via corners (26-neighborhood) were grouped to the same numbers. Avizo utilizes the 'labeling' module for this operation.

An open-source approach to this procedure is using the 'MorpholibJ' plugin in ImageJ/FIJI. This plugin combines Avizo's methods 'Separate Objects' and 'Labeling' in a single step called 'Distance-Transformation Watershed'⁴⁵. It was used to compare to the labelled volumes obtained from Avizo. Both programs yielded the same volumes, which ultimately resulted in the same graph metrics.

Adjacency extraction Calculations based on the reconstructed, post-processed, and 3D labeled (figure 7(B)) and binary (figure 7(A)) image were done using MATLAB. The basis of a graph is the adjacency matrix A , which describes the connection between nodes n through edges e . We extract A by investigating each voxel in the 3D data from the binary image (Figure 7(A)) and the label image (Figure 7(B)) and look two voxel "ahead" in each direction (orange cells in figure 7 (C)). If those "ahead positions" possess

Fig. 7 Extraction of the adjacency matrix A from the (A) binary image and (B) label image. (C) By investigating each voxel position and "look-ahead" positions, particles that initially were in contact are identified and (D) an edge between the particle's nodeID's is formed.

the same label as the current position (green cell in Figure 7(C)), the algorithm goes to the next position. Once the ahead position catches a "0" followed by a label different from the current position, a possible edge is detected. To confirm the presence of a contact, the algorithm looks at the position of the "0" in the binary image (figure 7(A)) to check whether this position was indeed the connection between two particles (labeled "1"). This "0" is the result of the watershed segmentation procedure between different label particles. If true, then an edge (Figure 7(D)) in the adjacency matrix is formed, and at the nodeID combination of "95-96" adds one voxel to the contact voxel. Intuitively, a particle contact can have more than one connecting voxel when investigating with this algorithm. Additionally, the "looking direction", i.e., from particle "96" to particle "95" or vice versa, affects the number of contact voxels that are counted. The resulting matrix, however, is strictly symmetric and needs to be converted into a logical array (consisting of 0's and 1's).

Building mathematical graphs All functions shown below are specific to MATLAB (version 2023b). The mathematical graph G is built through the function `graph()`, which uses the adjacency matrix A , the logical two-dimensional array obtained before as an input parameter. For illustration purposes, the adjacency of the 3D image in figure 7 was extracted to build G :

```
G = graph(A);
```

It can be plotted using

```
plot(G);
```

which results in the 2D representation in figure 8(A). The graph consists of nodes (black dots) and edges (blue sticks connecting

Fig. 8 Node-edge representation of a mathematical graph $G(n,e)$ (A) without and (B) with x - y - z information of the node's spatial location in 3D space.

the nodes). A dense collection of nodes with a high degree of interconnection can be seen as well as individual, unconnected nodes and isolated clusters. Figure 8(A) has few similarities with the initial label image in figure 7(B). A better representation can be obtained by adding coordinates to the individual nodes. The centroids of the label image can be used for this, and the graph plotted with

```
plot(G, "XData", coordinatesX, "YData", ...
coordinatesY, "ZData", coordinatesZ);
```

which yields figure 8(B), a 3D representation of G with spatial information. This way of illustrating G is more intuitive, revealing the complex network structure of the label image. To clarify, both ways of plotting G serve only illustrative purposes and do not interfere with any metric calculation. The spatial node locations will become important when simulating a Kirchhoff resistor network.

Metrics calculations The following network metrics were calculated using MATLAB:

The following PYTHON code was used to calculate the assortativity coefficient r_G :

```
import os
import networkx as nx
import scipy.io
import numpy as np
os.chdir(r'C:\Users\domin\Workspace_Directory')
mat = scipy.io.loadmat("matlab_workspace.mat")
Adj = mat.get("A")
A = np.matrix(Adj)
G = nx.Graph(A)
r = nx.degree_assortativity_coefficient(G)
b = nx.current_flow_betweenness_centrality(G)
```

First the workspace directory is set and the saved *.mat* file is loaded. The logical adjacency matrix is loaded from that file,

and a mathematical graph is built in Python using the NetworkX package. Finally, the assortativity coefficient is calculated in the last line.

Network resistance calculations using Kirchhoff Circuit Analysis

The reconstructed networks were interpreted as undirected graphs where certain nodes i and j were connected by edges with an electrical resistance R_{ij} ^{46,47} (Figure 9). We then applied an external potential difference $\Delta V = V_a - V_b$, (where, without limitation of generality, $V_a > V_b = 0$) to two current collectors ("probe") nodes a and b that were located at two opposite faces of the reconstructed volume and were in contact with all the particles located in the corresponding face. This creates an electrical field within the network, with defined electrical potentials V_i at all nodes and electrical currents I_{ij} flowing along edges from nodes with higher V_i to those with lower V_i . The probe resistance R_{probe} between the current collector and all other nodes was chosen much smaller, $R_{probe} \ll R_{ij}$, to reduce its effect on the result value.

We calculated potentials V_i and currents I_{ij} using Ohm's law:

$$I_{ij} = \frac{V_j - V_i}{R_{ij}}, \quad (8)$$

It determines the current flowing along each edge, and Kirchhoff's Current Law postulates current balance for each node:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{NN} I_{ij} = 0, \quad (9)$$

In the above equation, NN denotes nodes linked directly to node i . Currents that enter and leave a node have positive and negative signs, respectively.

Solving the system of eqs. (8) and (9) for the potential V_i gives:

$$V_i = \sum_{j=1}^{NN} \frac{V_j}{R_{ij}} / \sum_{j=1}^{NN} \frac{1}{R_{ij}}, \quad (10)$$

Table 1 Matlab metrics

Metric name	Metric symbol	Matlab Code
Number of nodes	N	<code>GNumNodes = numnodes(G);</code>
Number of edges	M	<code>GNumEdges = numedges(G);</code>
Node degree	k_i	<code>GDegree = G.degree;</code>
Graph degree	\bar{k}	<code>GAvgDegree = mean(GDegree);</code>
Node-to-node distances	$d_{i,j}$	<code>GDists = distances(G);</code>
-	-	<code>B = squareform(GDists);</code>
-	-	<code>DistanceArray = B(isinf(B));</code>
Reciprocal node-to-node distances	$d_{i,j}^{-1}$	<code>RecDist = 1./DistanceArray;</code>
Graph length	L	<code>GLength = mean(DistanceArray);</code>
Graph diameter	D_G	<code>GDiam = max(DistanceArray);</code>
Graph efficiency	E	<code>GEff = (sum(RecDist))/(GNumNodes*(GNumNodes-1))</code>

Fig. 9 Scheme used to calculate random network resistance with probe contacts at the faces of the network.

This equation links the potential at each node with the values of potentials V_j of its connected nodes^{48,49}. We re-calculate V_i for each node (except probe nodes, which serve as boundary conditions) iteratively, until the stationary redistribution of potentials and, correspondingly, currents is established. As stopping criteria, we use a condition when the sum of absolute values of deviations from the current balance (left side of eq.(9)) over nodes in the network except probe nodes drops to a negligibly small value, which is set equal to $1.0e^{-6}$ in our calculations.

The effective resistance between nodes a and b can be obtained after the calculation of the net current that flows through the probe nodes (node a or node b):

$$R_{net} = R_{ab} = \Delta V / \left| \sum_{j=1}^{NN} I_{aj} \right| = \Delta V / \left| \sum_{j=1}^{NN} I_{bj} \right|. \quad (11)$$

Author contributions

Dominik Perius: Writing - review and editing, Data curation, Methodology, Conceptualization.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

The data supporting this article have been included in the S.I.†. They include: Estimation of systematic reconstruction errors, distance distribution, representativity, porosity evaluation, and dead-ends as a function of CPC conductivity. The raw SEM image files, their processed binary and label image files, and the codes used to extract mathematical graphs from 3D images, calculate network metrics, and run Kirchhoff simulations are available from the author upon reasonable request.

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Notes and references

- 1 L. Wang and Y. Li, "A review for conductive polymer piezoresistive composites and a development of a compliant pressure transducer," *IEEE transactions on instrumentation and measurement*, vol. 62, no. 2, pp. 495–502, 2012.
- 2 I. Tavman and T. Evgin, "Metal particle filled, thermally conductive polymer composites for electronic packaging applications," in *2015 IEEE 21st International Symposium for Design and Technology in Electronic Packaging (SIITME)*, pp. 31–35, IEEE, 2015.
- 3 T. Wu, E. Gray, and B. Chen, "A self-healing, adaptive and conductive polymer composite ink for 3d printing of gas sensors," *Journal of Materials Chemistry C*, vol. 6, no. 23, pp. 6200–6207, 2018.
- 4 S. S. Siwal, Q. Zhang, N. Devi, and V. K. Thakur, "Carbon-based polymer nanocomposite for high-performance energy storage applications," *Polymers*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. 505, 2020.
- 5 R. Strümpfer and J. Glatz-Reichenbach, "Conducting polymer composites," *Journal of Electroceramics*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 329–346, 1999.
- 6 C.-W. Nan, Y. Shen, and J. Ma, "Physical properties of compos-

- ites near percolation,” *Annual Review of Materials Research*, vol. 40, pp. 131–151, 2010.
- 7 H. Pang, L. Xu, D.-X. Yan, and Z.-M. Li, “Conductive polymer composites with segregated structures,” *Progress in Polymer Science*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 1908–1933, 2014.
 - 8 J. F. Christ, N. Aliheidari, A. Ameli, and P. Pötschke, “3d printed highly elastic strain sensors of multiwalled carbon nanotube/thermoplastic polyurethane nanocomposites,” *Materials & Design*, vol. 131, pp. 394–401, 2017.
 - 9 R. Zallen and H. Scher, “Percolation on a continuum and the localization-delocalization transition in amorphous semiconductors,” *Physical Review B*, vol. 4, no. 12, p. 4471, 1971.
 - 10 F. Carmona, P. Prudhon, and F. Barreau, “Percolation in short fibres epoxy resin composites: conductivity behavior and finite size effects near threshold,” *Solid state communications*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 255–257, 1984.
 - 11 S. Kirkpatrick, “Percolation and conduction,” *Reviews of modern physics*, vol. 45, no. 4, p. 574, 1973.
 - 12 I. Balberg, “Tunnelling and percolation in lattices and the continuum,” *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 42, no. 6, p. 064003, 2009.
 - 13 D. Perius, M. Engstler, S. Blum, L. González-García, and T. Kraus, “Reconstruction of 3d conductive networks in metal-filled elastomer composites indicates dominance of contact resistances,” *Small Structures*, p. 2500234, 2025.
 - 14 A. V. Kyrlyuk and P. van der Schoot, “Continuum percolation of carbon nanotubes in polymeric and colloidal media,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 105, no. 24, pp. 8221–8226, 2008.
 - 15 J. V. Vas and M. Joy Thomas, “Monte carlo modelling of percolation and conductivity in carbon filled polymer nanocomposites,” *IET Science, Measurement & Technology*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 98–105, 2018.
 - 16 R. G. Struempfer, “Polymer composites for temperature and current sensors,” in *3rd International Conference on Intelligent Materials and 3rd European Conference on Smart Structures and Materials*, vol. 2779, pp. 377–382, SPIE, 1996.
 - 17 B. Reiser, L. Gonzalez-Garcia, I. Kanelidis, J. H. Maurer, and T. Kraus, “Gold nanorods with conjugated polymer ligands: sintering-free conductive inks for printed electronics,” *Chemical science*, vol. 7, no. 7, pp. 4190–4196, 2016.
 - 18 D. A. Vecchio, S. H. Mahler, M. D. Hammig, and N. A. Kotov, “Structural analysis of nanoscale network materials using graph theory,” *ACS Nano*, vol. 15, no. 8, pp. 12847–12859, 2021. PMID: 34313122.
 - 19 D. A. Vecchio, M. D. Hammig, X. Xiao, A. Saha, P. Bogdan, and N. A. Kotov, “Spanning network gels from nanoparticles and graph theoretical analysis of their structure and properties,” *Advanced Materials*, vol. 34, no. 23, p. 2201313, 2022.
 - 20 M. A. Kashfipour, N. Mehra, and J. Zhu, “A review on the role of interface in mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties of polymer composites,” *Advanced Composites and Hybrid Materials*, vol. 1, pp. 415–439, 2018.
 - 21 M. Cantoni and L. Holzer, “Advances in 3d focused ion beam tomography,” *MRS bulletin*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 354–360, 2014.
 - 22 M. Newman, *Networks: An Introduction*. Oxford University Press, 2010.
 - 23 N. Biggs, *Algebraic graph theory*. No. 67, Cambridge university press, 1993.
 - 24 J. M. Hernández and P. Van Mieghem, “Classification of graph metrics,” *Delft University of Technology: Mekelweg, The Netherlands*, vol. 1, 2011.
 - 25 G. Cahn, A. Barrios, S. Graham, J. Meth, A. Antoniou, and O. Pierron, “The role of strain localization on the electrical behavior of flexible and stretchable screen printed silver inks on polymer substrates,” *Materialia*, vol. 10, p. 100642, 2020.
 - 26 W. Brostow, “Radial distribution function peaks and coordination numbers in liquids and in amorphous solids,” *Chemical Physics Letters*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 285–288, 1977.
 - 27 J. Gurland, “An estimate of contact and contiguity of dispersions in opaque samples,” *Trans. Metallurgical Society of AIME*, vol. 236, pp. 642–646, 1966.
 - 28 H. Gundersen, R. Boyce, J. Nyengaard, and A. Odgaard, “The conneulor: unbiased estimation of connectivity using physical disectors under projection,” *Bone*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 217–222, 1993.
 - 29 D. Stauffer, “A. aharony introduction to percolation theory,” *London 2nd Ed: CRC*, 1994.
 - 30 M. Zulkarnain, A. Muhamad Husaini, M. Mariatti, and I. Azid, “Particle dispersion model for predicting the percolation threshold of nano-silver composite,” *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, vol. 41, pp. 2363–2376, 2016.
 - 31 R. Schueler, J. Petermann, K. Schulte, and H.-P. Wentzel, “Agglomeration and electrical percolation behavior of carbon black dispersed in epoxy resin,” *Journal of applied polymer science*, vol. 63, no. 13, pp. 1741–1746, 1997.
 - 32 M. Yourdkhani and P. Hubert, “Quantitative dispersion analysis of inclusions in polymer composites,” *ACS applied materials & interfaces*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 35–41, 2013.
 - 33 Y. S. Song and J. R. Youn, “Influence of dispersion states of carbon nanotubes on physical properties of epoxy nanocomposites,” *Carbon*, vol. 43, no. 7, pp. 1378–1385, 2005.
 - 34 R. Yang, A. Yu, S. Choi, M. S. Coates, and H.-K. Chan, “Agglomeration of fine particles subjected to centripetal compaction,” *Powder Technology*, vol. 184, no. 1, pp. 122–129, 2008.
 - 35 Y. Zhang, Z. Zhang, and J. Guan, “An empirical study of an agglomeration network,” *Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and Theoretical*, vol. 40, no. 41, p. 12365, 2007.
 - 36 M. E. Newman, “Mixing patterns in networks,” *Physical review E*, vol. 67, no. 2, p. 026126, 2003.
 - 37 P. Erdős, A. Rényi, *et al.*, “On the evolution of random graphs,” *Publ. math. inst. hung. acad. sci.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 17–60, 1960.
 - 38 M. E. Newman, “Assortative mixing in networks,” *Physical review letters*, vol. 89, no. 20, p. 208701, 2002.
 - 39 N. Abadi and F. Ruzzenenti, “Complex networks and interacting particle systems,” *Entropy*, vol. 25, no. 11, p. 1490, 2023.

- 40 V. Latora and M. Marchiori, "Efficient behavior of small-world networks," *Physical review letters*, vol. 87, no. 19, p. 198701, 2001.
- 41 M. E. Newman, "A measure of betweenness centrality based on random walks," *Social networks*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 39–54, 2005.
- 42 L. E. Oleas-Chávez, C. Pérez-Solà, and J. Herrera-Joancomartí, "Apples and oranges: On how to measure node centrality in payment channel networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 55469–55487, 2022.
- 43 G. Ruschau, S. Yoshikawa, and R. Newnham, "Resistivities of conductive composites," *Journal of applied physics*, vol. 72, no. 3, pp. 953–959, 1992.
- 44 P. Soille *et al.*, *Morphological image analysis: principles and applications*, vol. 2. Springer, 1999.
- 45 D. Legland, I. Arganda-Carreras, and P. Andrey, "Morpholibj: integrated library and plugins for mathematical morphology with imagej," *Bioinformatics*, vol. 32, no. 22, pp. 3532–3534, 2016.
- 46 B. Bollobas, *Modern Graph Theory*. Graduate Texts in Mathematics, New York, NY: Springer New York, 1998.
- 47 S. Redner, *Encyclopedia of Complexity and Systems Science*. New York, NY: Springer New York, 2009.
- 48 S. Kirkpatrick, "Percolation and conduction," *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, vol. 45, pp. 574–588, Oct 1973.
- 49 M. Siekierski and K. Nadara, "Modeling of conductivity in composites with random resistor networks," *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 50, no. 19, pp. 3796–3804, 2005. *Polymer Electrolytes*.
- 50 P. Hovington, D. Drouin, and R. Gauvin, "Casino: A new monte carlo code in c language for electron beam interaction —part i: Description of the program," *Scanning*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 1–14, 1997.

Supporting information

Fig. S1 Distribution of BSE information depth when hitting it with a 10kV electron beam at an inclination of 38°, the configuration that was used in FIB-SEM tomography.

Estimation of systematic reconstruction errors The electron beam probes a finite interaction volume that limits the resolution in x-y direction. We estimated the degree of averaging (or "smearing") that this causes by simulating the electron beam scattering in silver using a Monte Carlo algorithm (Monte Carlo Simulation of electroN trajectory in sOlid, CASINO v2.5.1.0⁵⁰). The distribution of escape depths for backscattered electrons (BSE) ensured that most of the BSE escaped from a depth matching the selected slice thickness (Figure S1), indicating that most of the material's information indeed comes from a single slice.

Fig. S2 3D reconstructed BSE images obtained at (A) 2kV, (B) 5kV and (C) 10kV show the effect of information depth on GT metrics (D) number of nodes N , (E) average graph degree \bar{k} and (F) graph efficiency E .

Lower acceleration voltages reduce the interaction volume and potentially increase resolution, but significantly lower the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and require longer acquisition times. The trade-off between cost and time makes 10kV a reasonable choice of acceleration voltage. We also probed this effect by carrying out

FIB-SEM tomography on a CPC of filler loading $\phi_{36vol\%}$ at three different acceleration voltages for the BSE images: After slicing of a 90nm rectangle, we recorded BSE images at 2kV, 5kV and 10kV for the same volume and all with a dwell-time of 6 μ s. We reconstructed the BSE images as described before and obtained graphs for each acceleration voltage. As expected, the SNR is low for 2kV (figure S2(A)). For the acceleration voltages 5kV (figure S2(B)) and 10kV (figure S2(C)), the SNR greatly increased and both images should be less affected by segmentation errors. The graph metrics verified this hypothesis as they only changed marginally between 5kV and 10kV. The number of nodes N (figure S2(D)) were around 900, while the average degree \bar{k} (figure S2(E)) was close to 3.6 and the graph efficiency E (figure S2(F)) close to 0.054. For 2kV on the other hand, all trends fell off: More particles were detected ($N = 1379$), the graph was less connected ($\bar{k} = 2.07$), and more as half as efficient ($E = 0.02$) as the graphs at higher kV. This is because low SNR leads to large noise before segmentation (using the same settings) might not be removed by the non-local means filtering. Subsequently, this affects other GT metrics directly, depending on the mathematical relation to the number of nodes. We see by this simple example that choosing a large acceleration voltage within the limit of information depth, probed by Monte Carlo simulations, a good SNR ensures representative GT metrics.

Future studies could utilize automated electron microscopy and TEM to increase resolution further, although this approach may be impractical for micron-sized particles. Here, nanoparticles as filler materials in polymer matrices might form a promising alternative.

Distance-Distribution

Fig. S3 Shortest node-to-node distance $d_{i,j}$ in a graph extracted from a volume of $\phi_{Ag} = 48vol\%$.

Figure S3 shows the distribution of (shortest) node-to-node distances $d_{i,j}$ in the shape of a Gaussian.

Representativity

Filler networks may have different properties at different length scales. All experimental techniques for the 3D reconstruction of microstructure are limited in the accessible volume, usually to sub-millimeter scales. Percolation is a scale-bridging phenomenon, and electrical conductivity being a macroscopic property, it is therefore not known *a priori* whether the analysis of a limited volume can be used to draw conclusions on conductivity.

In the following, we use global GT metrics to assess whether the FPN in CPC has scale-dependent properties. It is common to assume that successful processing will remove scale-dependent effects such as maldistribution or segregation. We tested whether the FIB-SEM tomography results indicate any remaining scale dependency. The absence of such dependencies implies that the analysis of limited volumes is sufficient for the network analysis of CPC.

Fig. S4 Length scale-dependent average degree \bar{k} , efficiency E , and assortativity coefficient r_G of the FPN in a CPC with $\phi_{Ag} = 48\text{vol}\%$

We calculated the assortativity coefficients r_G , average graph degrees \bar{k} , and graph efficiencies of an FPN cube of $(31.5\mu\text{m})^3$ at $\phi_{Ag} = 48\text{vol}\%$ and sub-volumes that we produced by isotropically increasing from cube's center until $(31.5\mu\text{m})^3$ was reached. Figure S4 shows metrics as a fraction of the resulting cubes' size l (see experimental section for details). The graph degrees (Figure S4a) increased to $\bar{k} > 4$ above $l = 3.8\mu\text{m}$, then more slowly until it converged to $\bar{k} = 5.4$ for $l > 20\mu\text{m}$. The efficiency E (Figure S4b) decreased from $E > 0.4$ to $E < 0.15$ below $l = 10\mu\text{m}$ and then slowly converged to $E = 0.06$ for $l = 31.5\mu\text{m}$. The smaller changes in \bar{k} and E after convergence are likely due to boundary effects: We removed 1250nm (half the particle size) isotropically from the outer planes and their corresponding graph of filler loading $48\text{vol}\%$ and recomputed the metrics from figures S4(A) and (B). Roughly 47% (793 out of 1663) of the particles were located on the outer planes. Removing these nodes from the graph resulted in a reduction of the average graph degree by 12% (from $\bar{k} = 4.97$ to $\bar{k} = 4.41$) and an increase in efficiency by 18% (from $E = 0.0733$ to $E = 0.0620$). The assortativity coefficients r_G fluctuated strongly at $l < 15\mu\text{m}$ and converged to 0.076 for $l \geq 15\mu\text{m}$.

It is conceivable that non-randomness only occurs at certain filler loadings, for example, because mixing processes become

more difficult as the viscosity of the slurry increases. All further analyses were therefore conducted with data calculated at a volume size of $l = 31.5\mu\text{m}$, which is more than double the required size for representativity.

The above results do not exclude non-randomness at larger scales. Future studies using micro-computed tomography ($\mu\text{m-CT}$) could be employed to capture FPNs at larger scales and probe representativity, as well as GT metrics.

Porosity evaluation through SEM snapshots

Fig. S5 Cross-sectional BSE images showing changes in the packing of the FPN in the range of $\phi_{Ag} = 36 - 52\text{vol}\%$. The scale bar is $10\mu\text{m}$ and applies to all images.

The SEM images shown in figure S5 were individual snapshots during the FIB-SEM tomography as described in the experimental section (10kV , 93pA , BSE detector, 90nm pixel size). The pores were outlined manually in red (using MS PowerPoint). For $\phi_{Ag} < 48\text{vol}\%$ no porosity was visible in the cross-sections. Above, the manually outlined pores were filled with white space (in MS PowerPoint) and exported to ImageJ. The fraction of white space was determined from the greyscale histogram via manual thresholding to estimate the area fraction of the pores.

Dead-ends as a function of CPC conductivity

Fig. S6 (A) 3D-plot of a mathematical graph $G(n,e)$ from a FPN with $\phi_{Ag} = 52 vol\%$. Nodes with $k = 1$ are highlighted in red. (B) Absolute number of $k = 1$ nodes as a function of CPC conductivity σ . (C) Relative number of $k = 1$ nodes with respect to all nodes in their respective graphs, as a function of CPC conductivity σ .

Particles that lie on the end of a path (within the 3D-reconstructed volume, at least) do not contribute to the overall CPC conductivity but are well-considered in distance-based metrics such as the average graph length \bar{L} or efficiency E . We hypothesized that the more reinforced and dense our FPNs became, the fewer dead ends would be present in our mathematical graphs.

To probe this, we counted nodes with $k = 1$ (highlighted red in figure S6(A)) as a function of silver loading, or CPC conductivity

σ . We find that the absolute (figure S6(B)) and relative (figure S6(C)) number of dead-ends decreases with σ until a steady-state is reached at the highest silver loadings, indicating a most dense structure of minimal dead-ends per volume.